

The Santal Revolt: A Forgotten Chapter in Bengal's Fight for Independence

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Abstract:

Although it is sometimes disregarded, the Santal Rebellion of 1855 represents a crucial period in Bengal's history of freedom struggles. This was a violent rebellion against British colonial rule and the exploitative practices of moneylenders, landowners, and corrupt officials, spearheaded by the Santal tribal chiefs Sidhu and Kanhu Murmu. During the colonial era, the Santals, an indigenous community living in what is now Jharkhand, West Bengal, and Odisha, faced extreme economic hardships as well as social abuses. Their uprising was a wider affirmation of their right to self-determination and resistance against oppression than just a response to these specific complaints. The Santal Revolt has not gained the same recognition as earlier uprisings like as the Sepoy Mutiny of 1857, despite its intensity and the high number of losses sustained by both sides. However, the uprising showed Bengali people's ability to resist British exploitation and paved the way for more movements in the region. It demonstrated the Santal people's strong ties to their homeland and culture, which they were prepared to sacrifice everything for. Regrettably, tribal histories have been marginalised and lack current evidence, which has led to their relative obscurity in popular historical narratives. My paper aims to shed light on the Santal Revolt as a critical moment in Bengal's fight for independence, emphasising the need to acknowledge and integrate such forgotten chapters into the broader discourse on India's colonial history.

Keywords: Santal Revolt, British colonialism, Bengal independence, indigenous resistance, tribal history

Introduction

There are many inspiring tales of bravery, selflessness, and defiance against British colonial control throughout the history of India's struggle for freedom. Some of these tales are still mostly unknown, even though many of them have been widely reported and honoured. One of the lesser-known but equally important uprisings is the Santal Revolt of 1855–1856, sometimes referred to as the Santal Hul. This uprising serves as a bitter reminder of the indigenous resistance against British exploitation, and it was led by the Santal tribe in the Bengal Presidency. One of the most important, albeit underestimated, uprisings in Indian history is the Santal Revolt. In a battle that showed both their desperation and their unwavering spirit, the indigenous Santals of the area rose up against the British colonial authority and their local allies, the zamindars (landlords). The Santal Revolt is still mostly forgotten in favour of other moments in India's independence movement, despite its significance. Using important literary and historical works as a guide, this dissertation seeks to illuminate this frequently ignored aspect of Bengal's struggle for independence by elucidating the background, reasons, and outcomes of the uprising.

Historical Background and Context

One of the biggest tribes in India, the Santal people, have historically lived in what is now Jharkhand, West Bengal, Bihar, and Odisha. For decades, the Santal people had lived in peace and seclusion, pursuing their agricultural traditions and maintaining their rituals and social hierarchies. The trees and the land they farmed were inextricably linked to their way of life. But when British control arrived, their life started to significantly alter. The Permanent Settlement of 1793, one of the new land revenue schemes implemented by the British, upended the Santals' customary agricultural methods. The Permanent Settlement turned the tribal lands into zamindari estates, controlled by landlords who were often outsiders to the community. The zamindars, often from outside the tribal communities, exploited the Santals through exorbitant rents, forced labour, and oppressive practices, pushing them into a cycle of debt and

poverty. The Santals were also subjected to the exploitative practices of moneylenders, who charged exorbitant interest rates, further exacerbating their economic distress.

The British courts favored the zamindars and moneylenders, leaving the Santals with little recourse to justice. This systematic exploitation led to a growing sense of frustration and anger among the Santals, who felt that their very existence was under threat. The Santals were subjected to oppressive taxation, forced labour, and exploitation by these landlords, moneylenders, and the British administration. The imposition of the alien land revenue system and the increasing encroachment on their lands led to widespread discontent among the Santals. The cultural and economic dislocation they experienced laid the groundwork for what would become a full-fledged rebellion.

One of the most comprehensive works that provides insight into the conditions leading up to the revolt is *The Santals: An Ethnographic Study* by Nirmal Kumar Bose. Bose meticulously details the social and economic life of the Santals, emphasising how the British policies alienated them from their traditional livelihoods. Similarly, Ranajit Guha's *Elementary Aspects of Peasant Insurgency in Colonial India* provides an analysis of how colonial oppression sparked various revolts, including the Santal Hul. Guha's work underscores the significance of the Santals' fight as not just a local or isolated incident but as part of a broader pattern of resistance in colonial India.

Causes of the Santal Revolt

The Santal Hul was primarily driven by economic exploitation, social injustice, and cultural alienation. The Santals, who were primarily agrarian, found themselves increasingly marginalized by the new economic order imposed by the British. The zamindars (landlords) and moneylenders, many of whom were non-tribals, exploited the Santals through exorbitant interest rates and manipulative practices that trapped them in a cycle of debt.

In addition to economic exploitation, the Santals faced social injustices that further fueled their anger. They were often subjected to physical violence and forced labor, and their women were targets of sexual exploitation by the landlords and British officials. These injustices were compounded by the cultural alienation they experienced as their traditional practices and customs were undermined by the imposition of British laws and Christian missionary activities.

The book *Adivasis and the Raj: Socio-economic Transition of the Hos, Oraons, and Santals (1820-1932)* by Biswamoy Pati provides a detailed account of how these factors led to the Santal uprising. Pati argues that the Santal Hul was a reaction not just to economic and social exploitation but also to the broader process of cultural marginalization. This perspective is crucial in understanding the revolt as more than just a peasant uprising; it was also a defense of the Santal identity and way of life.

The Course of the Revolt: A Fierce Expression of Resistance

The Santal Revolt officially began on June 30, 1855, when two brothers, Sidhu and Kanhu Murmu, mobilised about 30,000 Santals to declare a rebellion against the British authorities and their collaborators. The initial phase of the revolt was marked by a series of successful attacks on British outposts, zamindars, and moneylenders in the region. The Santals, armed with traditional weapons like bows and arrows, displayed remarkable courage and determination in their fight against the better-armed British forces.

The early successes of the Santal rebels sent shockwaves through the British administration. The revolt quickly spread across the Santhal Parganas and neighbouring areas, with the Santals setting up their own parallel government in some regions. They resisted British attempts to suppress the rebellion with a combination of guerrilla warfare tactics and direct confrontations.

However, the British soon retaliated with overwhelming force. The colonial government deployed a large contingent of troops, including the use of artillery, to crush the

rebellion. The British forces, aided by local collaborators, engaged in a brutal campaign of suppression, burning down villages and killing thousands of Santals. Despite their valor, the Santals were no match for the British military might, and by early 1856, the revolt was largely suppressed.

The book *The Santhal Rebellion: A Study in Tribal Revolt* by K.S. Singh provides a detailed narrative of the revolt, chronicling the key events and the role of leaders like Sidhu and Kanhu. Singh's work is invaluable in understanding the scale and intensity of the revolt, as well as the brutal methods employed by the British to suppress it.

Impact and Legacy of the Santal Revolt

The Santal Hul, though ultimately unsuccessful in achieving its immediate goals, had a profound impact on both the British administration and the subsequent independence movement in India. The revolt exposed the deep-seated grievances of the tribal communities and the extent of popular discontent against British rule. It also forced the British to reconsider their policies towards the Santals and other tribal groups, leading to some administrative changes in the region.

One of the immediate consequences of the revolt was the creation of the Santhal Parganas as a separate administrative unit in 1856. This was done in an attempt to address some of the grievances of the Santals and to prevent future uprisings. The British also introduced certain legal reforms, such as the Bengal Tenancy Act of 1885, which aimed to provide some protection to the peasants against the excesses of the landlords.

However, the legacy of the Santal Hul goes beyond these administrative changes. The revolt became a symbol of resistance and courage for future generations of freedom fighters in Bengal and beyond. It inspired a sense of pride and identity among the Santal community, who continue to celebrate the memory of Sidhu and Kanhu as heroes of their people.

The long-term impact of the Santal Hul on the Indian independence movement is explored in the book *Tribes and Independence in India* by Mahadev Chakravarti. Chakravarti argues that the Santal Revolt, along with other tribal uprisings, contributed to the broader nationalist movement by highlighting the importance of indigenous resistance to colonial rule. The revolt also served as a precursor to other significant uprisings, such as the Birsa Munda Rebellion in the late 19th century, which further galvanised the tribal communities in their fight against British oppression.

The Santal Revolt in the Context of Bengal's Freedom Struggle

The Santal Revolt should be understood as part of the larger context of Bengal's fight for independence. While the revolt was primarily a response to local grievances, it shared many characteristics with other anti-colonial movements in Bengal and elsewhere in India. Like the Indigo Revolt of 1859-60 and the Pabna Uprising of 1873, the Santal Revolt was rooted in the agrarian discontent that arose from the exploitative practices of the colonial system.

Moreover, the Santal Revolt can be seen as an early expression of the broader struggle for indigenous rights and autonomy that would later become an important aspect of the Indian independence movement. The Santals, like many other tribal communities in India, sought to resist the imposition of an alien system that threatened their land, culture, and way of life. In this sense, the Santal Revolt was not just a local or isolated event but part of a broader pattern of resistance against colonial domination.

The revolt also had a significant impact on the consciousness of the emerging nationalist movement in Bengal. The brutality with which the British suppressed the revolt, and the suffering of the Santal community, resonated with Bengali intellectuals and activists who were increasingly critical of colonial rule. The Santal Revolt thus contributed to the growing awareness of the need for a united struggle against British imperialism.

The Representation of the Santal Revolt in Historiography

Despite its importance, the Santal Revolt has often been neglected in mainstream historiography. For many years, the revolt was treated as a minor event, overshadowed

by larger uprisings such as the 1857 Sepoy Mutiny. The reasons for this neglect are manifold. First, the Santal Revolt occurred in a relatively remote and rural area, far from the urban centers that have traditionally dominated historical narratives. Second, the revolt was led by a tribal community that was often marginalised in the colonial records and later historical accounts.

However, in recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of the Santal Revolt. Scholars have begun to reexamine the revolt, emphasising its significance as a form of indigenous resistance and its impact on the broader anti-colonial struggle. The work of historians such as Ranajit Guha, in particular, has been instrumental in bringing the Santal Revolt into the spotlight. Guha's analysis of the revolt in the context of subaltern studies has highlighted the ways in which the Santal uprising was a challenge to both colonial authority and the social hierarchies imposed by the zamindari system.

Conclusion

Although it is sometimes disregarded, the Santal Rebellion of 1855–1856 is nevertheless a significant but little-known part of Bengal's struggle for independence. It was a broader declaration of Santal identity and fight against social and cultural marginalisation, rather than merely a response to economic exploitation. Even though the uprising was ultimately put down, it had a lasting impact on the colonial government and helped raise awareness of resistance, which eventually led to India's independence movement.

The legacy of the Santal Revolt remains relevant today as India continues to grapple with issues of indigenous rights, land ownership, and social justice. Recognizing and remembering the revolt is not only a way to honour the Santals who fought and died for their rights but also an essential part of understanding the broader history of resistance in India. As historians continue to uncover and reassess the forgotten chapters of India's past, the Santal Revolt stands as a powerful reminder of the complexities and diversity of the country's struggle for independence. Reexamining the Santal Hul serves as a reminder of the complex and multidimensional character of the Indian freedom

movement, which was a mass endeavour involving the efforts of numerous communities, including the tribal groups, rather than being confined to the deeds of a few notable individuals. The narrative of the Santal Revolt serves as a powerful reminder of the significance of recognising and commemorating these lesser-known historical episodes, which nevertheless have an impact on and motivate oppressed people' current efforts.

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